

This document forms section three of the University of Bath’s Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

3. Designing assessment – what to consider

Key points covered in this section:

- Establish the purpose, level, and focus of each assessment at the outset.
- Apply transparent criteria and identify appropriate forms of evidence.
- Ensure diverse, trained panels and fair consideration of personal circumstances.

Assessment processes can present challenges for those serving on panels, for example being asked to make decisions based on insufficient evidence, or being provided with a metric without any context of what it indicates. Taking time to design an assessment process can go a long way in making sure we are assessing as robustly and as fairly as possible. Careful design ensures everyone has access to the best available evidence, presented in the right form, to ensure a robust and fair decision.

To support fair, high-quality, and proportionate assessment, consider the approaches outlined below. These take account of the differing contexts in which assessment occurs. It is important for all those involved in the assessment to:

1. Agree on the purpose and level of the assessment

Be clear about the purpose of assessment (WHY are we looking to assess - is it to monitor, showcase (show off), incentivise, or reward?) and the level of assessment (WHO are we assessing - an individual, a group/ entity, or a higher education institute)?

These choices should inform both the method of assessment and what evidence is considered reliable or appropriate. The use of metrics as proxies in some forms of assessment has more impact on the entity being evaluated and therefore carries more risk, as demonstrated in Table 1.

For example, using metric proxies for institutional-level assessments for the purpose of monitoring progress carries much less risk (‘low’ in Table 1) than their use in individual-level assessments for the purpose of informing reward (‘high’ in Table 1).

Table 1 – Risk of using metrics as proxies for different levels and purposes of assessment (adapted from International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>)

Purpose	Level			
	Country	HEI	Group/ entity	Individual
To understand	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
To show off	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
To monitor	Low	Medium	Medium	High
To benchmark	Medium	High	High	High
To incentivise	Medium	High	High	High
To reward	High	High	High	High

Agreeing on the purpose and level at the outset is key to making sure that we design an appropriate assessment process.

2. Define the focus of the assessment

Understanding WHAT the focus of the assessment is will help determine what evidence is useful. For individuals or entities, assessment could focus on:

- *research outputs*
- *research contribution*, including impact, enterprise and engagement
or
- *total contribution*, including research outputs, research contribution (impact, enterprise and engagement), teaching (if relevant to the contract), and citizenship.

Figure 1 below provides some examples of different research assessment exercises, their focus, and types of evidence that might be considered in each case. These examples are not intended to be prescriptive, and assessors must design processes in a way that is tailored to their specific context.

Table 2: Examples of research assessment exercises, focus and associated evidence.

Examples reasons for assessment	Research output reward/ prize	Internal funding stage gate/ research prize/ sabbatical	Recruitment/ promotion/ probation/ global chairs/ career	Departmental/ Institute/ Centre review
What is likely to be assessed in this context?	Research output	Individual's contribution to research	Individual's total contribution	Entity's total contribution
What might be considered in assessment?	<p>Assessment of research outputs</p> <p>Other contributions to research & innovation</p>	<p>Assessment of research outputs</p> <p>Other contributions to research & innovation</p> <p>Consider including citizenship in assessment</p>	<p>Assessment of research outputs</p> <p>Other contributions to research & innovation</p> <p>Consider including citizenship in assessment</p> <p>Education and student experience contributions (where relevant to contract)</p>	<p>Assessment of research outputs</p> <p>Other contributions to research & innovation</p> <p>Consider including citizenship in assessment</p> <p>Education and student experience contributions (where relevant to contract)</p>

3. Set clear criteria

For any form of assessment to be responsible, fair, and transparent, it is important to have clear criteria that are understood by both assessors and those involved in the assessment.

Criteria should be:

- transparent to both assessors and to the individuals/ entities being assessed;
- relevant to the purpose and focus of assessment; and
- focussed on quality.

The criteria should be tailored to the type and purpose of assessment, so think carefully about what information is needed - and what is not - to make a reliable judgement.

4. Identify relevant and reliable evidence

Decide what quantitative and qualitative evidence best supports a robust assessment against the criteria.

Where the exercise includes an assessment of outputs, refer to the guidance on evidencing quality (Section 5) to see which evidence options are supported.

5. Design a suitable assessment process

Design processes that enable individuals or entities being assessed to bring forward relevant and reliable evidence against the criteria, in a format that the assessors can meaningfully review within the time available and considering their disciplinary expertise.

This ensures the person or entity being assessed can provide, and assessors can receive, the best possible evidence to inform a robust decision.

Consider how to avoid individuals submitting unreliable evidence (See Table 2, section 5).

6. Appoint a diverse and well-briefed panel

All research assessment should be conducted by a panel, not an individual. Panel members should complete unconscious bias and responsible research assessment training and have an opportunity to ask questions before assessment commences.

Wherever possible, panels should be diverse. However, this may place additional burden on minoritised groups (e.g. female colleagues in male-dominated fields). When inviting those panellists, make it clear that it is acceptable to decline, and think creatively about how to achieve diversity, for example considering asking colleagues from a range of career stages, other job families, other disciplines, or external organisations. See Section 9 for more guidance on assessment panels.

7. Consider personal context in individual assessments

Ensure individuals are given the opportunity, within the assessment process, to disclose any personal context or circumstances such as part-time working, career breaks, illness, disability, caring responsibilities.

These and other factors may impact an individual's capacity to contribute to research, teaching and/or citizenship and may not always be known to the assessor. While there is no perfect solution to account for personal circumstances, it is recommended - in line with student assessment practice - that all individuals are *still expected to meet quality markers* consistent with their career stage.

Panels should, however, consider accommodating *reductions in quantity or rate* of contributions.

Focusing on quality of contribution over quantity in the assessment process will reduce the likelihood of discrimination based on protected characteristic or temporary vulnerabilities.

[Click here to download an Assessment Design Checklist](#) to help you clarify these points.

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).